

1 **Can we project changes in fish abundance and distribution in response to climate?**

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26

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30

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32 Technical advances

33

34 **Abstract**

35 Large scale and long-term changes in fish abundance and distribution in response to
36 climate change have been simulated using both statistical and process-based models.
37 However, national and regional fisheries management requires also shorter term
38 projections on smaller spatial scales, and these need to be validated against fisheries data.
39 A 26-year time series of fish surveys with high spatial resolution in the North East Atlantic
40 provides a unique opportunity to assess the ability of models to correctly simulate the
41 changes in fish distribution and abundance that occurred in response to climate
42 variability and change. We use a dynamic bioclimate envelope model forced by physical-
43 biogeochemical output from eight ocean models to simulate changes in fish abundance
44 and distribution at scales down to a spatial resolution of 0.5°. When comparing with these
45 simulations with annual fish survey data, we found the largest differences at the 0.5°
46 scale. Differences between fishery model runs driven by different biogeochemical models
47 decrease dramatically when results are aggregated to larger scales (e.g. the whole North
48 Sea), to total catches rather than individual species or when the ensemble mean instead
49 of individual simulations are used. Recent improvements in the fidelity of biogeochemical
50 models translate into lower error rates in the fisheries simulations. However, predictions
51 based on different biogeochemical models are often more similar to each other than they
52 are to the survey data, except for some pelagic species. We conclude that model results
53 can be used to guide fisheries management at larger spatial scales, but more caution is
54 needed at smaller scales.

55

56 **Introduction**

57 Anthropogenic greenhouse gas emissions and associated warming strongly changes
58 ocean conditions, including temperature, salinity, ice cover, currents, oxygen, nutrients
59 and seawater acidity. These physical-biogeochemical changes affect the distribution,
60 abundance and productivity of phytoplankton, zooplankton and the fisheries that depend
61 on them (Perry et al., 2005; Pörtner, 2010; Cheung et al., 2011; Simpson et al., 2011;
62 Barange et al., 2014; Jennings and Collingridge, 2015; Fernandes et al., 2017; Maar et al.,
63 2018; Lotze et al., 2019). Such changes are expected to continue during the 21st century
64 under further global warming (IPCC, 2019) and have large implications for communities
65 and industries that depend on marine species for food and income (Roessig et al., 2004;
66 Cheung et al. 2012; Lam et al. 2012; Merino et al. 2012). A range of modelling approaches
67 has been developed to project future changes in marine ecosystems and fisheries (e.g.
68 Stock et al. 2011; Cheung et al. 2016). These models range from considering only the
69 ocean physical dynamics and low trophic levels (Dunne et al., 2010; Butenschön et al.
70 2016; Yool et al. 2013) to high trophic levels of fisheries and conservation interest
71 (Nielsen et al., 2018; Peck et al., 2018; Tittensor et al., 2018).

72 Species process-based bioclimate envelope models are commonly applied to study
73 biological responses to global warming (Cheung et al., 2011; Jones et al. 2012). For
74 example, the Dynamic Bioclimate Envelope Model (DBEM) is a combined mechanistic-
75 statistical approach that has been applied to a large number of marine species globally.
76 The DBEM projects changes in species distribution and abundance with explicit
77 consideration of known mechanisms of population dynamics, dispersal (larval and adult)
78 and ecophysiology, under changes in ocean temperature, salinity, oxygen, pH, upwelling,
79 sea-ice extent and habitat type (Cheung et al. 2008; 2009, 2011). Simulations with the
80 DBEM model show that high-latitude regions will experience high rates of species
81 invasion while the tropics will have high rates of local extinction by the end of the 21st
82 century under a high greenhouse gas emission scenario (Cheung et al., 2009; 2016). In
83 addition, maximum catch potential is projected to decrease in the tropics while some high
84 latitude regions may experience increases in potential catch because of changes in range
85 and size of exploited marine species as well as changes in primary productivity under
86 global warming (Cheung et al. 2010). Recently, the DBEM has been combined with a size-
87 spectrum model (Jennings et al., 2008) to evaluate the effects of inter-specific interactions

88 in projecting species distribution (Fernandes et al., 2013a). Size spectrum theory
89 accounts for energy transfer from primary production to individuals of different body
90 sizes to estimate abundance/biomass and their flows in marine ecosystems (Jennings et
91 al. 2008). The resulting integrated SS-DBEM (size-spectrum and DBEM model) projected
92 slower fish species shifts than in models that did not account for energy limitation. The
93 SS-DBEM has also been applied to several conservation issues (Jones et al., 2013; Queiros
94 et al., 2015) as well as socio-economic assessments in the North East Atlantic (Mullon et
95 al., 2016; Fernandes et al., 2017; Queiros et al., 2016) and developing countries
96 (Fernandes et al., 2016). However, projections of future species and fishery distributions
97 at local scales are uncertain (Payne et al., 2016, Cheung et al. 2016, Frölicher et al. 2016).

98

99 The model simulations are often not well constrained by observational data as the
100 available observations are limited in time and space. However, the availability of an
101 extensive compilation of data describing the distribution and abundance of North Sea
102 fishes from 1982 to 2007 (Simpson et al., 2011) provide us the opportunity to evaluate
103 the accuracy of projections of simulated fish abundance and distributions from the SS-
104 DBEM model. The data were collected by ICES co-ordinated bottom trawl surveys (ICES,
105 2012). We compare the data with simulations of fish abundance and distribution
106 conducted by linking multiple biogeochemical models and the SS-DBEM of commercial
107 fish populations. Thereby, we assess the likely reliability of future projections of fish
108 stocks under climate change and the impact of spread in ocean biogeochemistry
109 simulations on the fisheries projections. In addition, the combination of observation
110 based atmospheric boundary conditions and atmospheric boundary conditions from
111 Earth system models allows for an indication as to how the projections of fish abundance
112 and distribution are affected by the internal variability of these systems in contrast with
113 the more realistic variability from the reanalysis datasets. This understanding can be
114 applied when considering other ecological modelling approaches that occupy a similar
115 niche to SS-DBEM, many of which are the focus of inter-comparison efforts within the
116 international FISH-MIP initiative (Nielsen et al., 2018; Peck et al., 2018; Tittensor et al.,
117 2018; Heike et al., 2019).

118

119 **Methods**

120

121 We use output from three different ocean biogeochemical models (Table 1) to generate
122 the environmental and biological conditions (temperature, salinity, oxygen, pH, currents
123 and primary production) that drive the fish community model (size-spectrum dynamic
124 bioclimate envelope model; SS-DBEM; Fernandes et al., 2013a). The ocean
125 biogeochemical models are either run in fully coupled mode (i.e. coupled to a freely
126 evolving atmosphere, land, and sea-ice model) or run in hindcast mode (i.e. ocean-only
127 and forced at the ocean's surface with observed or model-derived atmospheric
128 conditions). We use multiple versions with different horizontal resolution of the three
129 ocean biogeochemical models to examine how an increase in spatial resolution and/or
130 different ocean biogeochemical model output influences the SS-DBEM simulations (Table
131 1). Furthermore, runs for the same model are used to compare different generations of
132 the same model and spatial resolutions. Fish distribution and abundance as simulated
133 between 1982 to 2007 are compared with 26 years of data from fish surveys by European
134 marine laboratories with a comparable spatial resolution (Simpson et al., 2011).

135

136

137 Ocean biogeochemical models

138 The choice of the biogeochemical model used to force the DBEM may have a significant
139 effect on forecasts of fish species abundance and distribution, especially in shelf seas
140 regions where predictions of the biogeochemical models can differ markedly. For this
141 reason, we chose to force the SS-DBEM with a diverse suite of output from three different
142 ocean biogeochemical models run under a range of different forcing modes in order to
143 cover the impact of the major sources of uncertainty in the biogeochemical forcing on the
144 fisheries mode. These forcing modes differ in the underlying model configuration used
145 and, as a result, in their relationship with real-world patterns of temporal variability. The
146 forcing modes used here are:

- 147 1. “Ocean-only hindcast mode”, where an ocean-only model is driven by
148 observationally-derived surface forcing at its air-sea interface. This mode
149 necessarily includes real-world trends and patterns of variability. There are a
150 number of methods available for creating the so-called reanalysis forcing used in
151 this mode, and this study exploits model simulations using several different
152 approaches.
- 153 2. “Fully-coupled mode”, where the model configuration includes an atmospheric
154 component that interacts dynamically with the ocean component. This mode
155 includes temporally-varying factors such as radiatively-active gases, so should
156 reproduce overall climate trends (e.g. global warming). But each fully coupled
157 model will show variability between runs whereas the observed data represent a
158 single realisation for each time point. For example, the real ocean experienced an
159 El Niño in 1997-1998. The coupled simulations may have had a La Niña, El Niño
160 or been neutral at this time. Only the averages and variances of this internal
161 variability are consistent with the real world.
- 162 3. “Coupled-forced ocean-only mode”, where an ocean-only model is driven by
163 surface forcing derived from a fully-coupled model. This mode is similar to the
164 first mode, but uses surface forcing output from a model running in the second
165 mode rather than observationally-derived forcing. As such, it may reproduce
166 observed long-term trends, but not specific temporal variability. This approach is
167 typically used where projection simulations into the future with relatively high
168 ocean model resolution or model downscaling are required (Yool et al., 2015).

169 Note that both ocean-only and coupled modes have limitations in the context of decadal-
 170 scale simulations: the forced ocean-only mode excludes any feedbacks between ocean
 171 and atmosphere (and the associated uncertainties), while the fully-coupled mode and
 172 coupled-forced ocean-only mode generate less directly-comparable data with present
 173 day conditions (particularly when phasing of internal variability is relevant). The use of
 174 a coupled prediction system as used in the WCRP Decadal Climate Prediction Project
 175 could reduce these shortcoming, however, these systems currently focus on physical
 176 climate and exclude biogeochemical components.

177

178 Table1 summarises the models from which output has been used to force the SS-DBEM
 179 model.

Name of model run	Horizontal ocean resolution	Forcing mode (Forcing dataset)
GFDL-hindcast	1°	Hindcast (CORE2 reanalysis)
GFDL-coupled	1°	Fully coupled
GFDL-coupled-esm2m	1°	Fully coupled
MEDUSA-coupled-forced	1°	Coupled-forced (HadGEM2-ES)
ERSEM-hindcast-lowres	0.25°	Hindcast (DFS 4.1)
ERSEM-hindcast-lowres2	0.25°	Hindcast (DFS 5)
ERSEM-hindcast-highres	0.125°	Hindcast (ERA 40 & ECMWF)

180 Table 1. Characteristics of the different ocean biogeochemical simulations used in this study.

181

182 The models are (datasets available as open access at Zenodo.org repository sith doi:
 183 10.5281/zenodo.3693596):

- 184 1) The National Oceanographic and Atmospheric Administration (NOAA) and
 185 Geophysical Fluid Dynamic Laboratory (GFDL) Earth System Model. GFDL is a
 186 global model where: 1) GFDL CM2.1 is using MOM4 for its physics (Delworth et al.
 187 2006) and TOPAZv0 for its biogeochemistry (Henson et al., 2010); and 2) GDFL
 188 ESM2M is using MOM4p1 for its physics and TOPAZv2 for its biogeochemistry
 189 (Dunne et al., 2010; 2012; 2013). TOPAZ simulates the cycling of carbon, nitrogen,
 190 phosphorus, silicon, iron, oxygen, alkalinity and lithogenic material, and includes
 191 three phytoplankton functional groups and one zooplankton. In this work the
 192 GFDL CM2.1 is run in both hindcast and fully-coupled modes, whereas GFDL
 193 ESM2M is run in fully coupled mode. The hindcast run here uses boundary
 194 conditions of bulk air properties, incoming fluxes of radiation and freshwater, and

195 surface wind stress as prescribed by the observationally-derived CORE-2
196 reanalysis product (Large & Yeager, 2009).

197 2) The European Regional Seas Ecosystem Model (ERSEM, Butenschön et al. 2016)
198 coupled to the NEMO ocean model (low resolution; Madec, 2008) and the
199 POLCOMS ocean model (high resolution; Holt et al., 2001). Hindcast mode
200 simulations are used in this study both at different resolutions and under different
201 observationally-derived atmospheric boundary forcing including DFS 4.1
202 (Brodeau et al., 2010), ERA 40 & ECMWF (Uppala et al., 005) and DFS 5 (Brodeau
203 et al., 2010). ERSEM is a biogeochemical model for the lower trophic levels of the
204 pelagic and benthic ecosystem, and uses a functional-groups approach that
205 incorporates four phytoplankton, three zooplankton and bacterioplankton to
206 simulate decoupled carbon and nutrient dynamics (Blackford et al., 2004;
207 Butenschön, 2016). All ERSEM models here are regional models where the highres
208 simulation is a regional set-up for the North-West European Shelf with details on
209 the configuration, initial conditions, boundary conditions and forcings are
210 available in (Holt et al. 2012). The two ERSEM lowres simulations are from a
211 NEMO-ERSEM configuration for the Atlantic Ocean at 0.25 degree (further details
212 in Memery and Allen, 2011; Allen et al., 2014). The two different versions of this
213 system reflect an update in model parametrisation and atmospheric forcing and
214 forecasting performance differences between using higher and lower results. Both
215 versions were included in the analysis in order to investigate how the resulting
216 changes propagate to the higher trophic level model.

217 3) The MEDUSA biogeochemical model (Yool et al., 2013a, 2013b) coupled to the
218 NEMO ocean model. Output from a coupled-forced ocean-only mode simulation is
219 used here, with the forcing derived from a CMIP5 simulation of the HadGEM2-ES
220 ESM (Collins et al., 2011). MEDUSA is lower complexity model, with two
221 phytoplankton, two zooplankton, three nutrients (N, Fe, Si) and slow-/fast-sinking
222 detritus compartments (Yool et al. 2013a).

223 In terms of biogeochemical complexity, MEDUSA is the simplest model considered here,
224 ERSEM is the more complex, with GFDL intermediate. Note that different versions of the
225 GFDL and ERSEM models were used here as well as different simulation configurations.

226 These differences relate to model evolution and improvement, including parameter
227 updates and the use of different spatial resolutions.

228

229 Fish model

230

231 The size-spectrum dynamic bioclimate envelope model (SS-DBEM) described in
232 Fernandes et al. (2013a) is used to simulate changes in abundance and distribution of fish
233 species. The SS-DBEM projects changes in species distribution and abundance with
234 explicit consideration of known mechanisms (Table 2) of population dynamics, dispersal
235 (larval and adult) and ecophysiology, under changes in ocean temperature, salinity,
236 upwelling, sea-ice extent and habitats (Cheung et al. 2011), and species interactions
237 based on size-spectrum theory and habitat suitability (Fernandes et al., 2013a). In SS-
238 DBEM, current distributions of the studied species are first estimated based on habitat
239 suitability (Close et al. 2006). This is done based on a global dataset of observed
240 abundance data from Cheung et al. (2008; available at fishbase.org which redirects to
241 maps hosted at aquamaps.com) overlaid with environmental data (temperature, salinity,
242 oxygen and pH at sea surface for pelagic species and at sea bottom for demersal species
243 as well as depth and distance to ice) from biogeochemical models described above. It is
244 assumed that the carrying capacity of each species in each area is partly dependent on
245 the inferred preference profiles which depend on the projected biogeochemical
246 conditions (e.g. temperature, salinity, pH and currents) but limited by primary
247 production. Simultaneously, the model considers each species' physiological preferences
248 and tolerances to temperature, and sensitivity of key parameters determining the
249 species' mechanisms (mortality, growth and length-weight relationship). Natural
250 mortality rate is estimated from an empirical equation (Pauly, 1980) which considers
251 weight, growth and temperature. The model growth algorithm (Cheung et al., 2011) is
252 derived from the von Bertalanffy growth function (VBGF; von Bertalanffy, 1951). Therein,
253 growth is viewed as the difference between anabolic and catabolic processes. The
254 temporal and spatial patterns of pelagic larval dispersal (Cheung et al., 2008) are
255 modelled by a two-dimensional advection-diffusion equation (Sibert et al. 1999; Gaylord
256 & Gaines 2000; Hunsdorfer & Verwer, 2003). Adult dispersal is calculated from the
257 dispersal or movement rate using an algorithm employed in an Eulerian spatial
258 ecosystem simulation model (Walters et al. 1999).

259 Table 2. Table summarizing main equations and parameters to consider the species
 260 mechanisms in SS-DBEM. Further details are given in the associated references.

Mechanism	Equation	Parameters
Growth = anabolism - catabolism (Pauly 2010; Cheung et al., 2011)	$G = HW^a - kW$ $H = g[O_2] * e^{-j1/T}$ $k = h[H^+] * e^{-j2/T}$	H = anabolism coefficient k = catabolism coefficient W = body weight a = anabolism exponent (0.5 to 0.95) W_{∞} = asymptotic weight The coefficients g and h were derived from the average W_1 , K, and environmental temperature (T) of the species reported in the literature.
Length-Weight	$W = a * L^b$	W = weight L = length
Size-spectrum production (Jennings et al., 2008; Fernandes et al., 2013)	$P = \exp(25.22 - E/kT) * W^{0.76}$	E = activation energy of metabolism k = Boltzmann's constant T = temperature in Kelvin ($^{\circ}C + 273$)
Intrinsic population growth rate (Hilborn & Walters, 1992)	$G = r * A * (1 - (A/KC))$	r = intrinsic rate of population increase A = the relative abundance KC = population carrying capacity
Larval dispersal (Hundsdoerfer & Verwer 2003; Cheung et al., 2008)		D = diffusion parameter (u, v) = velocity parameters LAV = larvae recruitment
Adult movement	$Cm * h^{-1}$	Cm = centimetre h = hour
Natural mortality	$M = -0.4851 - 0.0824 * \log(W_{inf}) + 0.6757 * \log(K) + 0.4687 * \log(T)$	W_{inf} = asymptotic weight K = von Bertalanffy growth parameter T = average water temperature in the animal's range.

261
 262 The SS component of the model addresses resource competition between different
 263 species co-occurring in any given cell by comparing the biomass that can be supported in
 264 the cell, as determined from primary production and the size-spectrum model, with the
 265 energy demanded by the abundance of the species predicted to inhabit this cell. This
 266 allocation is based on habitat suitability considerations and a generic group (other
 267 species) that can also compete for energy particularly if there is a surplus is available
 268 (Fernandes et al 2013a). If the energy demanded by all species in the cell exceeds the
 269 energy available, then the model allocates available energy to each species in proportion

270 to its energy demands. If the energy demanded by all the species is lower than the energy
271 available, the surplus energy is allocated according to the proportional energy demand of
272 the species present. The rate at which this energy can be assimilated is limited by
273 constraints on species' growth rates as described in Fernandes et al (2013a).

274
275 The model can consider fishing pressure in relation to maximum sustainable yield
276 (MSY). MSY is defined as the highest average theoretical equilibrium catch that can be
277 continuously taken from a stock under average environmental conditions (Hilborn &
278 Walters, 1992). Based on a simple logistic population growth function and under
279 equilibrium conditions, MSY can be defined as:

280

$$281 \text{MSY} = B_{\infty} * \text{intR} / 4$$

282

283 where intR is the intrinsic rate of population increase and B_{∞} is the biomass at carrying
284 capacity (Schaefer, 1954; Sparre and Venema, 1992). In our application, the intR values
285 are calculated based on natural mortality (Pauly 1980; Cheung et al., 2008). This is an
286 approximation and not as reliable as estimates of biomass using survey-based methods
287 (McAllister et al. 2001; Pauly et al., 2013). However, these estimates have proven to be
288 significantly correlated with those from aggregated stock assessments (Froese et al.,
289 2012; Fernandes et al., 2013). This fishing mortality is applied uniformly across all the
290 cells according to scenarios of fishing (e.g. 0.8 or 1.2 times MSY) and do not aims to
291 reproduce exact past fisheries effort distribution. Therefore, in this work no fishing
292 mortality scenario was activated in the model projections. Future work based on catch
293 and fishing effort reconstructions (Watson et al., 2017; Taconet et al., 2019) may allow
294 estimates of historical non-uniform fishing mortality to be included in models.

295 Fisheries survey data

296 Eleven standardised and long-term fisheries surveys from 1982 to 2007 covering all year
297 seasons (Simpson et al., 2011) were used to validate the model (Fig. 1). These surveys
298 (AFBI Iris Sea Q3, AFBI Irish Sea Q1, CEFAS Celtic Sea, CEFAS Eastern Channel, CEFAS
299 Irish Sea, CEFAS North Sea, CEFAS Western Channel, FRS NW Scotland Q1, FRS NW
300 Scotland Q4, ICES IBTS North Sea Q1, MBA Western Channel) were collated by Simpson
301 et al. (2011) and now available at ICES DATRAS online database ([www.ices.dk/marine-
302 data/data-portals/Pages/DATRAS.aspx](http://www.ices.dk/marine-data/data-portals/Pages/DATRAS.aspx)). To control for the differing effort between
303 surveys, the swept area for each haul (over 22 000 hauls with six different gears) was
304 calculated using estimates of wing-spread for Grande Ouverture Verticale trawls from
305 Fraser et al. (2007):

306

$$307 \text{ Area swept} = (((6.85 * (\log_{10}(\text{depth}))) + 5.89) * \text{distance}) / 10^6$$

308

309 Where area swept is in km², and depth and distance are in meters. A tow speed of 4 knots
310 (7.4 km h⁻¹) was assumed for the duration of the haul, except for data from the Celtic sea
311 collected by Agri-Food and Biosciences Institute, Belfast, UK, where the data were
312 originally provided as number of individuals per 3 nautical miles (~5.6 km). The 10⁶
313 scaling converts from m² to km².

314

315 Catchability estimates (Table 3) were used to provide more robust estimates of
316 abundance for each species by sizes (Sparholt 1990; Fraser et al., 2007). An average
317 catchability estimate was applied to similar species, where individual species values were
318 not available.

319

$$320 \text{ Corrected abundance} = \text{uncorrected abundance} * (1/\text{catchability})$$

321

322 Table 3. Table summarizing catchability correction values by species and sizes (based on
 323 Simpson et al., 2011).

Species	Size (cm)	Catchability correction
<i>Chelidonichthys lucerna</i>	1-20, 21-22, 23-25, 26-30, 31-33, 34, 25-80	0.21, 0.18, 0.17, 0.16, 0.14, 0.13, 0.11
<i>Clupea harengus</i>	1-100	0.1
<i>Gadus morhua</i>	1-31, 32-36, 37-39, 40-42, 43-45, 46-47, 48-49, 50-51, 52-53, 54-55, 56, 57-58, 59, 60-61, 62, 63-64, 65, 66, 67, 68, 69-70, 71, 72, 73, 74, 75, 76, 77, 78, 79, 80, 81, 82, 83, 84, 85, 86, 87, 88, 89, 90, 91, 92, 93, 94, 95, 96, 97-200	0.16, 0.17, 0.18, 0.19, 0.2, 0.21, 0.22, 0.23, 0.24, 0.25, 0.26, 0.27, 0.28, 0.29, 0.3, 0.31, 0.32, 0.33, 0.34, 0.35, 0.36, 0.37, 0.38, 0.39, 0.4, 0.41, 0.42, 0.43, 0.44, 0.45, 0.46, 0.47, 0.48, 0.49, 0.5, 0.52, 0.53, 0.54, 0.55, 0.56, 0.58, 0.59, 0.6, 0.61, 0.63, 0.64, 0.65, 0.67
<i>Glyptocephalus cynoglossus</i>	1-20, 21, 22-23, 24, 25, 26-27, 28-31, 32-34, 35-38, 39-60	0.11, 0.09, 0.08, 0.07, 0.06, 0.05, 0.04, 0.03, 0.04, 0.05
<i>Hippoglossoides platessoides</i>	1-5, 6, 7, 8, 9, 10, 11, 12, 13, 14, 15, 16-19, 20, 21, 22, 23, 24, 25, 26, 27, 28, 29, 30-60	0.11, 0.16, 0.2, 0.23, 0.26, 0.29, 0.32, 0.34, 0.36, 0.37, 0.38, 0.39, 0.38, 0.37, 0.35, 0.33, 0.31, 0.29, 0.26, 0.22, 0.19, 0.15, 0.1
<i>Lepidorhombus whiffiagonis</i>	1-60	0.06
<i>Melanogrammus aeglefinus</i>	1-11, 12, 13, 14, 15, 16, 17, 18, 19, 20, 21, 22, 23, 24, 25, 26-27, 28-33, 34-35, 36-37, 38, 39, 40, 41, 42, 43, 44, 45, 46-80	0.01, 0.04, 0.06, 0.09, 0.11, 0.13, 0.15, 0.17, 0.19, 0.2, 0.21, 0.23, 0.24, 0.25, 0.26, 0.27, 0.28, 0.27, 0.26, 0.25, 0.24, 0.22, 0.21, 0.2, 0.18, 0.16, 0.14, 0.12
<i>Molva molva</i>	1-11, 12-200	0.05, 0.1
<i>Raja montagui</i>	1-200	0.15
<i>Sardina pilchardus</i>	1-100	0.1
<i>Scomber scombrus</i>	1-100	0.19
<i>Scophthalmus maximus</i>	1-21, 22-24, 25-28, 29-31, 32-34, 35-38, 39-41, 42-200	0.05, 0.06, 0.07, 0.08, 0.09, 0.1, 0.11, 0.12
<i>Scyliorhinus canicula</i>	1-200	0.22
<i>Solea solea</i>	1-22, 23-60	0.04, 0.05
<i>Sprattus sprattus</i>	1-100	0.1
<i>Trachurus trachurus</i>	1-100	0.19
<i>Trisopterus esmarkii</i>	1-100	0.19
<i>Trisopterus luscus</i>	1-11, 12-60	0.05, 0.1

324

325

326 Model validation

327 All survey data were aggregated into a $0.5^{\circ} \times 0.5^{\circ}$ cell grid to match the SS-DBEM grid. To
328 compare simulated changes with observations from surveys, time-series at different
329 aggregation scales (e.g. aggregating all the cells, or all the species in a cell) were extracted
330 and projected biomass was scaled to lie between 0 and 1. Since multiple species at
331 multiple cells are considered, we ensured that results were comparable by omitting time-
332 series of survey data with more than 3 years of missing data. Then, time-series output
333 from the SS-DBEM models were extracted for the remaining years, species and cells
334 where there were data from the surveys at the $0.5^{\circ} \times 0.5^{\circ}$ grid and yearly resolution. This
335 restricted the data that could be analysed to the time period 1982 to 2007 (26 years) and
336 to 18 species, including 5 pelagic species: Atlantic herring (*Clupea harengus*), Atlantic
337 mackerel (*Scomber scombrus*), Atlantic horse mackerel (*Trachurus trachurus*), European
338 pilchard/sardine (*Sardina pilchardus*), sprat (*Sprattus sprattus*); and 13 demersal
339 species: haddock (*Melanogrammus aeglefinus*), plaice (*Hippoglossoides platessoides*),
340 witch (*Glyptocephalus cynoglossus*), megrim (*Lepidorhombus whiffiagonis*), cod (*Gadus*
341 *morhua*), common sole (*Solea solea*), lesser spotted dogfish (*Scyliorhinus canicula*),
342 Norway pout (*Trisopterus esmarkii*), turbot (*Scophthalmus maximus*), tub gurnard
343 (*Chelidonichthys lucerna*), pouting/bib (*Trisopterus luscus*), ling (*Molva molva*) and
344 spotted/cuckoo ray (*Raja montagui*). We chose these species as they are both
345 commercially important for local fisheries and include some species with distributions
346 centred on the North Sea, Celtic Sea and Irish Sea alongside those with more northerly
347 (high latitude) and southerly (low latitude) centres of distribution.

348

349 We compared model projections with data at different scales, spanning those used in
350 previously published projections of climate-driven changes in fish distribution and/or
351 abundance (e.g. Fernandes et al., 2016; Fernandes et al., 2017; Jones et al., 2013; Mullan
352 et al., 2016; Queiros et al., 2015; Queiros et al., 2016; Coccoli et al., 2018). We consider
353 the following (Fig. 1): (1) all the cells are considered for all the species (325 cells and 18
354 species) named “Species by cells” in a first spatial validation; (2) time series for individual
355 species aggregated over all cells (“All species” or individual species) in a first temporal
356 validation; and, (3) time series for each of the 325 cells where all the species are
357 aggregated (“All cells” or individual cells) in a spatial and temporal validation, and, (4) a
358 time series for each species aggregating all the cells for which survey information was

359 available (species cells sum). A species could be present in between 75 (turbot) and 325
 360 (Herring) cells.

361

362

363 Figure 1. Example of survey data for cod (one of the species with more coverage) in Celtic Sea, Irish Sea and
 364 North Sea (left side). Scheme of spatial and temporal validation resolutions in the right side.

365

366 The time-series 1-3 were generated for both the survey data and the model projections
 367 and comparisons between data and projections were reported as absolute error (AE):

368

$$369 \quad AE_j = |p_j - x_j| \quad (1)$$

370

371 where, p is the scaled biomass predicted in a SS-DBEM model in a particular year for a
 372 species, and x is the scaled biomass from the survey. The use of scaled values enables
 373 direct comparison of data and SS-DBEM projections across species and levels of
 374 aggregation.

375

376

377 **Results**

378

379 The main environmental drivers of SS-DBEM and other fisheries models are temperature
380 and net primary production, which are obtained from the ocean biogeochemical models.
381 Most forcing models show an increasing trend in temperature over the 1982-2007 period
382 for which we have fish survey data (Fig 2). There is spread in the absolute temperature
383 with some models simulating temperatures of 10.5 to 11.5 °C in cells included in the fish
384 surveys, while others projecting temperatures of 9.5 to 10.5°C (Fig. 1). Trends in primary
385 production are more uncertain than those in temperature, with some models showing no
386 trends, while others project decreases of 10-15% over the 1982-2007 period.

387

388 Figure 2. Simulated annual sea surface temperature and net primary production changes from 1982 to
389 2007 of different biogeochemical models. The reported values are the average across cells where fish
390 survey data is considered. The time-series has been smoothed with a five-year moving average. Solid lines
391 indicate reanalysis projections and dashed lines fully coupled projections.

392 There are multiple examples where there is a good fit between SS-DBEM projections and
 393 survey data with high correlation (Pearson) among projections and survey data (Fig. 3):
 394 herring between 0.73 (GFDL-hindcast) and 0.96 (GFDL-coupled), Cod 0.76 (MEDUSA-
 395 coupled-forced), haddock between 0.92 (ERSEM-hindcast-lowres2) and 0.95 (GFDL-
 396 coupled), sprat between 0.88 (GFDL-hindcast) and 0.96 (ERSEM-hindcast-lowres), sole
 397 between 0.81 (ERSEM-hindcast-highres) and 0.91 (GFDL-coupled),

398

399 Figure 3. Scaled biomass projections (5 years moving average) for 5 pelagic and 13 demersal species with
 400 different biogeochemical model forcings in cells where fish survey abundance data were also available.
 401 Note that Cod projections failed with several inputs from biogeochemical models.

402

403 pouting between 0.65 (GFDL-coupled-esm2m) and 0.78 (ERSEM-hindcast-highres),
404 horse mackerel between 0.69 (ERSEM-hindcast-lowres) and 0.76 (MEDUSA-coupled-
405 forced), plaice between 0.49 (MEDUSA-coupled-forced) and 0.87 (ERSEM-hindcast-
406 highres), or cuckoo ray between 0.79 (GFDL-coupled-esm2m) and 0.99 (GFDL-coupled).
407 Witch is another species where most models seem to perform well with correlations
408 between 0.59 (ERSEM-hindcast-lowres2) and 0.75 (GFDL-coupled), but where one model
409 performs very bad showing high negative correlation of -0.74 (ERSEM-hindcast-lowres).
410 Model runs for mackerel and megrim do not perform so well, but still show competitive
411 correlations between 0.58 (GFDL-hindcast) and 0.66 (ERSEM-hindcast-lowres) for
412 mackerel, and between 0.45 (ERSEM-hindcast-highres) and 0.54 (GFDL-coupled) for
413 Megrim. Model runs for dogfish and tub can achieve high correlations of 0.74 (GFDL-
414 coupled) and 0.87 (GFDL-coupled) respectively, however some of the models show also
415 very low performances of 0.36 (ERSEM-hindcast-lowres2) and 0.3 (MEDUSA-coupled-
416 forced) respectively. Finally, a few species show very low correlations for all model runs
417 (Ling between 0.01 and 0.28) or even negative correlations: turbot between -0.17 and
418 0.44, pout -0.41 and -0.47, and pilchard between -0.14 and -0.54.

419 These results suggest that an increase in spatial resolution does not necessarily mean a
420 higher performance in species biomass trends. The highest resolution model (ERSEM-
421 hindcast-highres) sometimes shows higher correlation with survey data for some
422 demersal species (pouting and plaice) than the lowest resolution models. However, for
423 other pelagic and demersal species often the lowest resolution model runs (GFDL) are
424 the ones showing the highest correlations (e.g. herring, haddock, sprat, sole). In other
425 cases, although the higher resolution model runs may show superior correlations these
426 may be very close to lower resolution model correlations and not be statistically
427 significant different from them (paired t-test).

428 Fits tend to improve in later years in the time series for several species, perhaps reflecting
429 the reduction in fishing mortality (Simpson et al., 2011) and its effect on survey data
430 distributions in later years (Fig. 3). However, this could also be the result of a more
431 representative area being covered by the surveys since their geographical extend has
432 increased over time (Baudron et al., 2020).

433

434 The different biogeochemical models generate rather similar error, with more variation
435 between models for the pelagic fish species and for sharks and rays (Fig. 4). In “Species
436 by cells” comparisons (1) median error is 0.42-0.44, with similar results between runs.
437 At the “All species” or individual species level (2), the median of the error is 0.27-0.31.
438 This means that when looking at the species aggregated biomass, the SS-DBEM is more
439 reliable and that there is rather little impact of the biogeochemical chosen for
440 environmental conditions projection. The lowest error values correspond to the
441 reanalysis run (GFDL) and the latest runs (ascending order in Table 1) showing that
442 improvements in the forcing models (e.g. new data or reparameterization) are translating
443 into more reliable projections from the SS-DBEM. However, the performance differences
444 are small in most species and levels of aggregations which highlight the higher role of the
445 model uncertainty in the fisheries model. With “All cells” (3) the error range is 0.16-0.18
446 which shows the ability of the forcing and SS-DBEM model to forecast variations in total
447 biomass at 0.5° resolution. Ensemble model results are within those error ranges and do
448 not improve performance when working with “All cells” (Fig. 2i).

449 In general, errors are smaller for “All species” (2) than for the species in each cell
450 (“Species by cells”, 1). The mean and standard deviation for the former are 0.25 ± 0.11 and
451 0.40 ± 0.14 for the latter (Fig. 4). This confirms higher model performance for total
452 biomass than for species biomass in each cell. The results by species can help to identify
453 where the SS-DBEM needs improvement. In general, widely distributed pelagic species
454 (e.g. Herring, Horse mackerel, mackerel, sprat) have among the highest errors at the
455 “Species by cells” (1) level, but a better performance when the total species biomass in
456 each cell is considered (“All species”, 2). This indicates that there is something
457 systematically wrong with the way that the SS-DBEM handles those species, even though
458 the general allocation of biomass to pelagics is reasonable. Note, however, that the
459 bottom trawl surveys are not designed to sample pelagic species (ICES, 2016) and
460 relatively short tows with limited time in the water column can provide a misleading
461 picture of abundance and distribution for predominantly shoaling species (Battaglia et al.
462 2006). At the “Species by cells” (1) level the species for which the models perform best
463 are pout, haddock, plaice and lesser-spotted dogfish, all bottom-dwelling species that are
464 effectively sampled by the survey gear (Fraser et al 2007; Walker et al. 2017).

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Figure 4. Median of the absolute error at different scales of analysis for species and overall (bold) where (1) all the cells are considered for all species (325 cells and 18 species) named “Species by cells”; (2) time series for each species where all the cells are considered aggregated (“All species”); (3) time series for each of the 325 cells where all the species are aggregated (“All cells” (species sums)); and, (4) a time series is produced for each species aggregating all the cells with survey information (species cells sum). See text for additional explanation.

471 **Discussion**

472
473 While there was generally good agreement among biogeochemical models on the sign
474 and extent of the temperature increase, the trends in primary production were less
475 consistent. These differences can be attributed to a variety of factors such as model
476 uncertainty and internal model variability (Hawkins and Sutton, 2009; Naujokaitis-Lewis
477 et al., 2013; Payne et al., 2015, Cheung et al. 2016, Frölicher et al. 2016). Especially on
478 local-to-regional scale (i.e. North-East Atlantic), model uncertainty and internal
479 variability may play a dominant role in differences across model runs (Hawkins and
480 Sutton, 2009; Chust et al. 2014; Frölicher et al. 2016). Here it seems that model
481 uncertainty/resolution may play a bigger role than internal variability given that
482 uncertainty in NPP trends is as large or larger for models forced in the same way
483 (reanalysis) than for models that are forced differently (i.e. coupled or forced), but share
484 the same biogeochemical model. For example, Laufkötter et al. (2015) have identified
485 how uncertainty in the representation of underlying physiological processes influences
486 the trends in net primary production. Here, we can observe in the multiple runs of
487 historical and forced GFDL the uncertainty due to internal variability seems to be smaller
488 than model uncertainty in marine biogeochemical models. Detailed comparisons of six
489 different biogeochemical models (including MEDUSA and ERSEM used here) in
490 physically-identical model simulations have shown the importance of the underlying
491 modelled biogeochemistry on biogeochemical indicators including primary production
492 (Kwiatkowski et al., 2014). However, the main characteristics of the trends of the two
493 sets of environmental variables from the biogeochemical models used in this study to
494 drive the fisheries simulations are in line with the results from global model data sets
495 (Steinacher et al. 2010, Laufkötter et al. 2015, Frölicher et al. 2016).

496
497 Existing studies have made projections of fish distribution and abundance at scales
498 ranging from higher resolution (Cheung et al., 2011; Burrows et al., 2014; Molinos et al.,
499 2015) to higher level of aggregation (Mullom et al., 2016; Fernandes et al., 2016). Many
500 studies, including those for fisheries management, only need information at relatively low
501 level of aggregation such as LMEs, FAO areas, seas, ICES areas, EEZs or subregions
502 (Blanchard et al., 2012; Fernandes et al., 2016; Mullon et al., 2016; Queiros et al., 2015;
503 Queiros et al., 2018). Applications not dependent on high resolution data are often used

504 for management and economic research, linked with long term scenarios (Mullon et al.
505 2016; Queiros et al., 2018) or ecological studies looking at overall impacts on specific
506 species or habitats (Queiros et al., 2015). However, other studies and management
507 research aims for or requires a higher level of detail such as cells of $0.5^\circ \times 0.5^\circ$ or smaller
508 as in the case of ICES rectangles or even $1 \times 1 \text{ km}^2$ for local marine spatial planning or
509 studies of shifts of species abundance centroids (Jones et al., 2013; Queiros et al., 2016;
510 Fernandes et al., 2017; Coccoli et al., 2018). Some applications requiring higher resolution
511 are marine spatial planning (Queiros et al., 2016, Coccoli et al., 2018) or studies about
512 shifts of species abundance centroid (Jones et al., 2013).

513

514 The widely reported regime shift in the late 1980's in the North Sea (Reid and Edwards
515 2001, Beaugrand 2004, Weijerman, Lindeboom et al. 2005) suggested to have affected
516 several species in this analysis (Fig. 4) providing evidence of biogeochemical drivers for
517 the shifts. The reported shifts are sparse such as the increase in horse mackerel, sprat and
518 reduction of cod in abundance (Reid, Borges et al. 2001, Alheit, Mollmann et al. 2005)
519 despite other species shifts might have occur. However, a recent publication shows
520 species distribution shifts for 17 main widely distributed species in the North East
521 Atlantic (Baudron et al., 2020). The comparison of the performance of the models at
522 different resolutions shows, in general, that outputs are more reliable when aggregated
523 at larger time- and space- scales. As such, these would be favoured for reporting.
524 However, users of projections will often seek projections for individual species of
525 conservation or fisheries significance and small areas that reflect those accessible to, or
526 used by, a defined fishing fleet. For example projections at small space and time scales
527 may be requested to assess the abundance of "choke" species under climate change, given
528 their potential effects on the capacity of a fishery to access available quota (Baudron and
529 Fernandes, 2015).

530

531 Predicted latitudinal shifts of species are difficult to compare with empirical data since
532 data collection is often focused in areas where species have been distributed in the past
533 (ICES, 2016). This is the case of our survey data (Simpson et al., 2011) where sampling
534 centres on the Celtic Sea, Irish Sea and North Sea (up to ICES area IVa) or sprat surveys
535 that are focused in the Baltic Sea. Sparse data are available for ICES area IVa (ICES, 2016)

536 and North of the Faroe Islands. However, species latitudinal shifts have been observed in
537 the global catch data (Cheung et al., 2013). There is limited knowledge North of ICES area
538 IVa due to limited international cooperation to share survey data and even South of ICES
539 area IVa the surveys mostly target higher value demersal species (ICES, 2016). However,
540 the aim of models such as SS-DBEM is not to predict accurately (Planque et al., 2016;
541 Dickey-Collas et al., 2014) where the species are present or will be present, but to
542 highlight the species and areas where changes are more likely to happen, and generate
543 uncertainty estimates (Planque et al., 2016; Payne et al., 2016). There is a trade-off
544 between goodness-of-fit and generalization power (Fernandes et al., 2015). Models that
545 very precisely represent the present have a performance that deteriorates faster as
546 projections are made further into the future (Rutterford et al., 2015).

547

548 At the highest output resolution we considered (0.5×0.5 degrees by year and species)
549 error was relatively high. Rutterford et al. (2015) also compared observed data with
550 predicted values using a GAM to project changes in distribution and abundance of
551 demersal species, obtaining correlations >0.5 for a 10 year forecast, but decreasing to
552 ≤ 0.5 at 10 year or longer-term forecasts. Statistical methods based on observations may
553 have limited value in long-term forecasting of systems that are expected to depart
554 markedly from their past state due to the long-term impacts of climate change (Barnsley
555 et al., 2007; Queiros et al., 2015; Payne et al., 2016). In addition, statistical models that
556 consider interactions between species are rare (Fernandes et al., 2013b), whereas this is
557 more common in mechanistic models (Blanchard et al. 2012; Fernandes et al., 2013a;
558 Thorpe et al., 2015). The survey data used in statistical models are relatively costly to
559 obtain and in many regions such observations are sparse or non-existent (e.g.
560 Bangladesh; Fernandes et al., 2016).

561

562 Variation between biogeochemical models is limiting predictions for several pelagic
563 species, whereas for most of the remaining species the choice of the biogeochemical
564 model makes little difference. Therefore, for most of the species the validation performed
565 here can guide improvement in fisheries models. Another alternative is the use of model
566 ensembles as a means of increase the reliability of projections (Araújo & New, 2007; Jones
567 et al., 2012; McKenna et al., 2013; Scales et al., 2015). In this study, the ensemble of
568 forcing-model runs did not affect performance of the SS-DBEM on average, but reduced

569 the probability of extreme errors, which would be an important consideration for some
570 applications. Outcomes from any given ensemble are highly dependent on the diversity
571 of constituent models, so it is unlikely our result can be generalised. Recent research is
572 moving towards ensembles of biological models which could benefit from similar
573 validation exercises (Lotze et al., 2019; Hermann et al., 2019) and collaborative protocols
574 for integration and comparison of multiple fisheries models (Tittensor, et al. 2018).

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579

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602 **DATA AVAILABILITY STATEMENT**

603 The environmental conditions used in this study from biogeochemical models is available
604 as open access at Zenodo.org repository with doi: 10.5281/zenodo.3693596. The latest
605 (and updated) survey data used for the models validation is available through ICES
606 (www.ices.dk/marine-data/data-portals/Pages/DATRAS.aspx). Dr. Louise Rutterford
607 can be contacted for applying catch correction factors to other species not considered in
608 this publication (lar210@exeter.ac.uk). Biological parameters can be consulted in
609 fishbase website (<https://www.fishbase.org>). SS-DBEM projections are made available
610 through FISH-MIP initiative (after embargo period), but Dr. Jose A. Fernandes also
611 provide them on request (jfernandes@azti.es).

612

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